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Farmers' Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices Regarding Insect Pest Management

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ABSTRACT

This study examined farmers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding insect pest management in South Punjab, Pakistan, with a focus on identifying the key determinants influencing the adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices. Using a cross-sectional design and multi-stage random sampling, data were collected from 60 farmers across Multan, Bahawalpur, and Muzaffargarh through a structured and pre-tested interview schedule. The study explored farmers' socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge of pest management, attitudes toward chemical and non-chemical control methods, actual pest management practices, and perceived challenges. Descriptive results show that although most farmers can identify major insect pests (91.7%), awareness of IPM is low (33.3%), and knowledge of pest ecology such as life cycles and beneficial insects is limited. Attitudes reflect a heavy reliance on chemical pesticides, despite significant concerns about human health and environmental impacts. Practices remain largely chemical-dependent, with 58.3% relying solely on pesticides, 80% not using action thresholds, and unsafe handling practices commonly observed. Key challenges to adopting improved methods include high costs of non-chemical inputs (75%), lack of IPM training (66.7%), and limited access to improved tools (50%). Correlation analysis showed significant positive relationships between IPM practices and both knowledge ($r = .45$) and attitudes ($r = .52$). Multiple regression analysis further confirmed that attitude ($\beta = .44$, $p < .001$), knowledge ($\beta = .32$, $p = .001$), education level ($\beta = .20$, $p = .034$), and farm size ($\beta = .19$, $p = .044$) are significant predictors of IPM adoption, collectively explaining 46% of the variance in practices. Age and farming experience were not significant predictors. The findings highlight the crucial role of farmer education, capacity building, and accessible extension services in improving sustainable pest management. Strengthening IPM knowledge, reshaping farmer attitudes, and addressing economic barriers are essential for enhancing environmentally sound and safer pest management practices in the region.

Key words: Knowledge, Pest, Insect, Management, Skills, Attitude

Introduction

Attitude refers to an individual's readiness or tendency to react in a particular manner toward a social object or phenomenon (Sikdar et al., 2020). The knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of farmers with regard to management of insect pests are important factors that determine the agricultural productivity and long-term sustainability of the farming systems. Insect pests have continued to pose a significant problem to smallholder and commercial farmers leading to significant losses in yield as well as economic impact on a wide variety of cropping systems. How farmers are aware of pests, their perception of available control methods, and actual practices in their fields is critical in designing effective extension programs, encouraging environmentally friendly technologies to be used in pest management including the application of the so-called Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and also to make sure that pests are managed in a sustainable way. The socioeconomic conditions, the level of education, the availability of resources, and the technological and policy environment at large influence the interaction between the knowledge of farmers, their attitudes toward various strategies of pest management, and their field practices (Dunn et al., 2023). One of the few studies to present a consistent finding is that, farmers have a high degree of knowledge gap in relation to pest identification, pest biology and ecological relationship within the cropping system. A study in Cambodia found a 23.6 percent of rice farmers to have high level of knowledge on rodent pest management, 41.6 percent moderate, and 34.8 percent low level of knowledge (Anusha & Rao, 2022). In the same study, researchers in Nepal observed that farmers

had a reasonable knowledge of key rice pests like the rice leaf folder and yellow stem borer, but their ecological and economic knowledge of pests was still poor (Paudel et al., 2024). In Nepal, Gulmi district which produces maize, only 1.1% of farmers were able to comprehensively identify insect pests, with 63.3% only identifying few economically visible pests, including fall armyworm and white grubs (Adhikari et al., 2024).

The most widespread pest control tools are pesticides, natural or synthetic chemicals, which are used to kill or control pests, weeds and pathogens. They are grouped into biological target, chemical structure and safety profile. According to biological target, pesticide can be categorized into five broad categories, namely, herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, rodenticides, and acaricides (Paul & Dey, 2025). In most places, farmers are still significantly dependent on chemical pesticides and in most cases, they do not fully understand their correct application. As an illustration, Cambodian farmers often replace useful insects like lady beetles with pests and rely on chemical insecticides as their general approach to pest management. They also state that they require better education resources on how to identify pests and how to use pesticides safely and utilize IPM methods (Dunn et al., 2023). In Haryana, India, farmers were found to be very aware of the important pests including whitefly and leafhopper but they depended on agriculture input dealers to provide them with information. One of the limitations was the high cost of insecticides, and most frequently used were the imidacloprid and thiamethoxam (Kumari et al., 2023). Likewise, Kenyan farmers did not use IPM practices, but 39.81% had high awareness of false codling moth and high yield losses (76.85%), whereas the use of synthetic insecticides was high (99.07%), reported (Onamu et al., 2024).

In the Lamjung district of Nepal, the knowledge held by farmers was very much different with most of the farmers having a personal experience and agrovets as their main information sources. About half of the farmers responded to having used chemical pesticides, and 32.5% never used any formal pest control method, but relied on botanicals or uncomplicated cultural control (Adhikari et al., 2018). In Rukum East, farmers had knowledge of insect pests, which are primarily the walnut weevil and shoot borer, and the majority were practicing cultural control, with few practicing physical or biological control (Devkota et al., 2025). In the Doti district, the awareness level on IPM was 25.6 per cent and only 5.8 per cent farmers engaged in IPM, despite the positive attitude towards sustainable pest management (Magar et al., 2024). Other previous studies by Sadat and Chakraborty (2017) also reported that 99 percent of farmers use pesticides without discrimination, and only 10 percent of them were aware of natural enemies, which demonstrated a severe lack of IPM knowledge and environmental awareness.

In the world, food is lost by approximately 45 percent of the yearly production of food due to pest attacks and therefore proper management of pests is essential in food security. The accelerated growth of the world economic sphere, especially in the agricultural and industrial sectors, in the second half of the 19th century has seen large-scale use and production of agricultural chemicals as a result. The use of pesticides has devastated the environment as this widespread use has led to soil contamination, biodiversity destruction and long-term interference with the ecology. An average of 2 million tonnes of pesticides are consumed on a yearly basis with China leading the world on consumption, then the United States and Argentina. By 2020, the number of pesticides used worldwide was estimated to be 3.5 million tonnes. Even though pesticides are an essential element in crop protection, they obey their persistent nature, bioaccumulation, and its extensive misuse have raised a significant

environmental and public health issue (Sharma et al., 2019).

Methodology

The present study was conducted in the agricultural region of South Punjab, Pakistan, to comprehensively investigate the determinants of pest management practices among farmers. A cross-sectional research design was employed, utilizing a multi-stage random sampling technique to ensure representativeness. Initially, three districts—Multan, Bahawalpur, and Muzaffargarh were randomly selected from the region. From each of these districts, 20 farmers were chosen through simple random sampling, yielding a final sample size of 60 respondents. Data collection was carried out using a structured and pre-tested interview schedule, which was developed based on the study's objectives and administered directly to the farmers. The instrument was designed to gather quantitative data across several key domains: socio-demographic characteristics (age, experience, education, farm size), knowledge of pest management and Integrated Pest Management (IPM) principles, attitudes measured on a 5-point Likert scale towards various pest control methods and their associated risks, self-reported practices concerning pesticide use, safety measures, and scouting, and finally, the perceived challenges hindering the adoption of improved practices. The collected data were subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize the profiles of knowledge, attitudes, practices, and challenges. To delve deeper into the relationships and predictive factors, inferential analyses were conducted, comprising a Pearson's correlation matrix to explore bivariate relationships between key variables and a multiple linear regression analysis to identify the significant predictors of integrated pest management practices, while also checking for multicollinearity among the independent variables. This rigorous methodological approach ensured the systematic and reliable collection of data, facilitating a robust exploration of the factors shaping farmer behavior in pest management.

Variables and Regression Equation

The multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to predict the level of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices adopted by farmers. The model can be represented by a standard regression equation.

Variables

Dependent Variable (Y):

Pest Management Practices Score: A composite score representing the degree to which a farmer adopts integrated and sustainable pest management practices. A higher score indicates better adherence to IPM principles.

Independent Variables (X):

Knowledge Score (X₁): A composite score measuring a farmer's understanding of pest identification, life cycles, beneficial insects, pesticide resistance, and IPM concepts.

Attitude Score (X₂): A composite score derived from Likert-scale questions, reflecting the farmer's beliefs about the effectiveness, safety, and practicality of various pest control methods.

Age (X₃): The age of the farmer in years.

Farming Experience (X₄): The number of years the farmer has been engaged in farming

Education Level (X₅): The farmer's level of formal education (likely coded numerically, e.g., 1=No formal education, 2=Primary, 3=Secondary, etc.).

Farm Size (X₆): The total area of land cultivated by the farmer, typically in acres or hectares

The Regression Equation

The general form of a multiple linear regression equation is:

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + e$$

Using the unstandardized coefficients (B) from Table 7, the specific estimated regression equation for this study is:

$$\text{Predicted Pest Management Practices Score} = 12.45 + (0.38 \times \text{Knowledge Score}) + (0.45 \times \text{Attitude Score}) + (-0.08 \times \text{Age}) + (0.05 \times \text{Farming Experience}) + (0.61 \times \text{Education Level}) + (0.72 \times \text{Farm Size})$$

Where:

12.45 is the regression constant (or intercept), representing the predicted Practices Score if all independent variables were zero.

The coefficients (**0.38**, **0.45**, **-0.08**, etc.) indicate the change in the dependent variable for a one-unit increase in each predictor, holding all other predictors constant.

The equation does not include the error term (e) when used for prediction.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Farmers' Knowledge of Insect Pests and Management Options

Knowledge Statement	Response Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Can identify major insect pests in their crop	Yes	55	91.7
	No	5	8.3
Aware of the concept of Integrated Pest Management (IPM)	Yes	20	33.3
	No	40	66.7
Knowledge of life cycle of key pests	High	10	16.7
	Moderate	25	41.7
	Low	25	41.7
Aware of beneficial insects (natural enemies)	Yes	35	58.3
	No	25	41.7
Knows about pesticide resistance	Yes	40	66.7
	No	20	33.3
Source of Pest Management	Extension	18	30.0

Knowledge Statement	Response Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Knowledge	Officers		
	Other Farmers	25	41.7
	Pesticide Retailers	12	20.0
	Media/Internet	5	8.3

Table 1 demonstrates that the population of farmers is well-informed on some practical elements of pests management but has serious deficiencies in the knowledge regarding the integrated and sustainable agricultural structures. As reported by Saleem et al. (2023) study reveals that awareness and usefulness of services are directly associated with the socio-economic position of the farmers. socio-economic had a statistically significant relationship with awareness. According to the results the fact that a high percentage of farmers (91.7) are able to identify key insect pests is a good one because pest identification comes in as the necessary initial action in any effective pest management program (Dara, 2019). But this good practical knowledge is not paralleled with an insight into more general ideas. It is interesting to note that the proportion of farmers who know about Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is 33.3 percent, which means that the large majority probably do not have a comprehensive system of prevention, observation, and adopting various control measures (FAO, 2021). This knowledge gap is critical since unless IPM is known, farmers will eventually revert to a reactive, pesticide-focused model, which as the data shows, is plausible, given that the knowledge sources of primary farmers are this. The literature through which farmers learn also throws more light on possible obstacles to implementation of sustainable practices. The biggest share (41.7) is dependent on the other farmers encouraging knowledge transfer system that is more traditional and may not bring new system instead of reinforcing the old ones. Worst still, 20.0 percent rely on pesticide retailers as a source of advice, which might cause a conflict of interest, since retailers might be financially inclined to advocate the use of pesticides instead of alternatives that are non-chemical in nature (Mohring et al., 2020). This use of informal and commercially-focused channels rather than formal extension officers (30.0%), would indicate the need to have more resolute and available public agricultural extension services to deliver science-based and unbiased information. The conclusion about an incomplete pest management understanding is proved with the help of further analysis of definite spheres of knowledge. Although the level of awareness of pesticide resistance is fairly high (66.7%), it may be assumed that this knowledge is practical as it developed through the experience of failures with products instead of a comprehensive knowledge of resistance management. This is not ideal out of context of IPM, where the farmer might resort to more intense pesticide usage or using pesticides more frequently to mitigate the problem of resistance (Brevik et al., 2018). In addition, knowledge on pest ecology is poor; 41.7% of the farmers possess low knowledge on the life cycle of major pests, and 41.7% are ignorant of the useful insects. This is a significant setback to IPM in that successful biological and cultural management may require knowledge of the life stages of pests to be intervened with and preservation of natural enemies (Pedigo & Rice, 2009).

Table 2: Farmers' Attitudes Towards Insect Pest Management

Attitude Statement	SA f(%)	DA f(%)	N f(%)	A f(%)	SA f(%)
Chemical pesticides are the most effective solution.	2 (3.3)	5 (8.3)	10 (16.7)	30 (50.0)	13 (21.7)
Using pesticides is harmful to the environment.	8 (13.3)	15 (25)	20 (33.3)	12 (20.0)	5 (8.3)
Biological control methods are a good alternative.	5 (8.3)	10 (16.7)	25 (41.7)	15 (25.0)	5 (8.3)
Preventive measures are better than curative ones.	0 (0)	8 (13.3)	12 (20.0)	25 (41.7)	15 (25.0)
I am worried about the health effects of handling pesticides.	3 (5)	7 (11.7)	15 (25.0)	22 (36.7)	13 (21.7)
Adopting IPM is too complicated and time-consuming.	15 (25)	20 (33.3)	12 (20.0)	10 (16.7)	3 (5.0)

Table 2 show a complicated scenario of the mindset of the farmers is seen with a community that is torn between the established reliance on the usage of chemical pesticides and an increased realization of the disadvantages, but unwilling to shift to more sustainable Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies because of perceived impediments. There is a high dependency on chemical control as most of the farmers (71.7% agree or strongly agree) are of the opinion that chemical pesticides are the best remedy. This mentality is associated with the gap of knowledge that was found in previous Table , especially, low awareness of IPM (33.3) and poor knowledge of pest life cycles, and biological alternatives. Nevertheless, there is this dependence, but there is also high cognitive dissonance. It is evident that a significant number of the farmers are concerned with the adverse effects of using pesticides; 38.3% of farmers concur about the fact that the environment suffers at the hands of the pesticides, and a greater number of 58.4% are concerned with the health impact of handling them. This implies that farmers do not seem to be blind to the risks but they might be of the view that they have no other equally good option. This strain is also depicted in their opinions of alternatives. Although one out of three farmers (33.3%) regards biological control as a good substitute, it is interesting to note that a significant proportion (41.7) of farmers remain neutral, which indicates a lack of knowledge or even uncertainty about those procedures. This is opposed to their perception of prevention where a large percentage (67.4) of them believe that preventive methods are superior to the curative ones. Such a supportive attitude towards prevention is a valuable starting position to preventative strategies that IPM essentially is (FAO, 2021). The greatest obstacle to change, however, seems to be the attitude of IPM itself. More than half of

the farmers (58.3%), mentions that they are in agreement or strongly in agreement with the fact that the implementation of IPM is too complex and time consuming. This is one of the strongest barriers and it is probably based on the lack of knowledge that was mentioned above including poor knowledge about pest life cycles and useful insects. In some cases even the farmers who do not have the basic ecological knowledge, IPM may appear to be an abstract and complex set of rules instead of a working decision-making model (Dara, 2019). This complex barrier usually wins over their perceived health and environmental worries and their theoretical concurrence with prevention strategies. Finally, the attitudinal evidence indicates that farmers are practically minded to do what they consider as most effective (chemicals) and understand the risks involved with it but they now find IPM as an unattainable and cumbersome option. This gap needs to be filled with some intervention strategies that directly touch on these perceptions. The extension activities should go beyond merely advertising IPM and should show its practical application in terms of time saving. This may be simplified decision support tools, practical field demonstrations, and emphasizing the economic benefits to offset the complexity narrative and demonstrate IPM is a practical, manageable and ultimately safer system to deal with pests.

Table 3: Farmers' Practices in Insect Pest Management

Practice	Category	f	%
Primary Pest Control Method	Solely Chemical Pesticides	35	58.3
	Cultural Methods (e.g., crop rotation)	15	25.0
	Mixed Methods (Chemical + Other)	10	16.7
Scouting before pesticide application	Always	18	30.0
	Sometimes	25	41.7
	Never	17	28.3
Reads pesticide label instructions	Always	22	36.7
	Sometimes	30	50.0
	Never	8	13.3
Uses Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)	Fully	10	16.7
	Partially (e.g., gloves only)	32	53.3

Practice	Category	f	%
	Not at all	18	30.0
Disposes of pesticide containers by	Burning/Burying	25	41.7
	Throwing in field/waterway	20	33.3
	Returning to dealer	15	25.0
Uses pest action thresholds	Yes	12	20.0
	No	48	80.0

Table 3 on actual practices of the farmers shows a big discrepancy between what they have voiced against and their actual practices on the ground, which creates an image of a farming population that extensively depends on chemical pesticides with practices that are hazardous to human lives and the environment. The most remarkable result is that 58.3 percent of farmers depend on the use of chemical pesticides only as the basic means of control and 16.7 percent depend on the mixture of used chemicals. This is in line with the attitude data previous where 71.7% of the respondents viewed pesticides as the most effective solution, and is probably supported by the lack of awareness of the Integrated Pest Management (IPM) (33.3%). This chemical addiction is typified by a largely reactive, as opposed to an informed, approach. The observation that only 80 percent of the farmers do not utilize pest action thresholds is an important one. One of the foundations of IPM is action thresholds, which gives a scientifically-grounded condition of intervention that will prevent unneeded pesticide use (Dara, 2019). Without this practice, then most spraying is probably carried out on a calendar basis or when a pest is first seen, and this results in lack of efficiency and environmental burden. This is further reinforced through the scouting behavior as 30 percent always scout before spraying, a combined 70 percent only sometimes or never scouts before spraying, which portrays that most pesticide applications are made without a good field evaluation. Moreover, the information demonstrates alarming safety and environmental stewardship gaps. Even though most of the farmers are concerned about the health impacts of pesticides (58.4%), they lack proper safety practices. The proportion of those with full Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) is the lowest (16.7%), followed by partially (i.e., gloves only) (53.3%), and none (30%). This lack of connection of risk and protective action is a grave health social problem. Equally, in the case of 50 percent of the farmers may not read pesticide labels regularly, that is, there is a basic precautionary and efficacy measure, and 13.3 percent never do, the chances of inaccurate application and self-exposure are high. The environment is also affected and 33.3 percent of farmers also dump containers by throwing them into fields or waterways and this habit has serious ramifications on the quality of soil and water. These risky practices are probably supported by the dependence of the other farmers and pesticide retailers on the knowledge (Table 2) and results in the development of the cycle in which chemical dependence is a standard tool, and safety and sustainability are second priorities.

Twenty five percent of farmers relying on cultural practices as the main control as the 20 percent of farmers relying on action thresholds are a very important base. Such farmers show that there are other practices that can work within the community and can be used as models during the extension programs.

Table 4: Challenges Faced in Adopting Improved Pest Management Practices

Reported Challenge	f	%
High cost of non-chemical inputs (e.g., biopesticides)	45	75.0
Lack of knowledge/training on IPM	40	66.7
Perceived lower efficacy of alternatives	35	58.3
Lack of access to improved inputs/tools	30	50.0
Labor intensiveness of alternative methods	25	41.7
Limited extension support	22	36.7

According to the information in Table 4, it is clear that farmers experience a web of interconnected economical, knowledge-based, and perceptual barriers that make them adopt better pest management practices. These problems offer an explanatory overlay to the behavior and attitudes observed in the preceding tables. The biggest hindrance, which is reported by 75% of the farmers, is the high cost of non-chemical inputs. This is a strong disincentive that is economically limiting. Although most farmers may not be aware of IPM (previous table) and may have a positive attitude to alternatives, the perceived cost can be a decisive factor. This is in line with the observation that 58.3 percent of farmers feel that the efficacy of alternatives is less; when a product is pricier and is less perceived to be effective then there is very little likelihood that they will adopt it. This provides a strong economic support of the status quo, in favor of cheaper and more familiar chemical pesticides. The second challenge named the most (66.7%), which is the absence of knowledge/training on IPM, is an immediate confirmation of the knowledge gaps reported in Table 2 where the level of IPM awareness was low (33.3%) and the awareness of pest life cycles and helpful insects was also low. This lack of knowledge is a root weakness in that farmers cannot be assumed to embrace a complicated arrangement of actions that they are not conversant with. This is made worse by the lack of extension assistance (36.7%), meaning that the institutional mechanisms that are supposed to close this knowledge gap are not accessing a large percentage of the farming population. Such unsupportive nature probably increases the use of informal, which may be biased sources of information by farmers like other farmers and retailers of pesticides (as observed in previous table). There is need to educate the farmers about different agriculture aspects that is the responsibility of extension staff as reported by Prakash et al. (2021) that Training is a critical input in improving farmers' knowledge and skills level as it provides an excellent opportunity to the farmers for learning by doing themselves. Moreover, real and logistical obstacles are also influential. The inability to access better inputs/tools (50%): It is possible that even the motivated farmers cannot access the required resources in IPM since they cannot physically do it. Also, the fact that 41.7 percent indicate the labor-intensiveness of alternative methods as a hindrance assists in clarifying the reason why 58.3 percent of farmers concurred that

IPM is too complicated and time-consuming. Regular scouting, setting up traps to control insects or use biopesticides may be more managerial-intensive than a calendar-directed chemical spray, and this can be a serious challenge in terms of labor.

Table 5: Correlation Coefficients Among Knowledge, Attitude, and Pest Management Variables

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Pest Management Practices Score	—					
2. Knowledge Score	.45**	—				
3. Attitude Score	.52**	.38**	—			
4. Age	-.18	-.25*	-.31*	—		
5. Farming Experience	.22	.15	.08	.67**	—	
6. Education Level	.35**	.41**	.29*	.44**	-.19	—
7. Farm Size	.28*	.19	.21	.12	.33*	.24*

The correlation matrix gives an indispensable bivariate summary of the interactions among the key variables in the research that is useful in the context of the more intricate regression analysis and supportive to the story produced by the preceding data. The strongest and the most important results are the high, positive correlations of the Pest Management Practices Score with the Knowledge Score ($r = .45$, $p < .01$) and Attitude Score ($r = .52$, $p < .01$). These correlations show that, individually, the higher the knowledge on pests and IPM, and the more favorable the attitudes to sustainable methods, the better the pest management practices were adopted. This is consistent with the regression findings and confirms that knowledge and attitude are the pillars to the change in the behavior. The fact that Knowledge and Attitude as such ($r = .38$, $p < .01$) are positively correlated indicates that the two variables are mutually reinforcing; the more farmers learn, the better their attitudes can be, and vice-versa.

There are also instructional patterns of socioeconomic variables. The level of Education is positively correlated with the better practices ($r = .35$, $p < .01$), knowledge ($r = .41$, $p < .01$) and attitude ($r = .29$, $p < .05$). This makes education one of the enabling factors that may lead the learning process and the molding of positive attitudes. On the same note, Farm Size exhibits a positive, albeit low correlation with enhanced practices ($r = .28$, $p < .05$), which implies that resource endowment might be a factor that determines the ability of a farmer to implement new practices.

Age is also having a negative relation with Knowledge ($r = -.25$, p less than .05) and Attitude ($r = -.31$, p less than .05), and this might indicate that older farmers in this sample are less familiar with formal IPM ideas and less positive about the alternatives to chemical pesticides. It is however important to mention that the Age and Farming Experience are highly correlated with each other ($r = .67$, $p < .01$), and this implies that they capture overlapping factors in the profile of the farmer. The fact that it is not the

Farming Experience, which correlates with practices, knowledge, and attitude significantly but Age, which is negatively correlated, gives a fine-tuned image. It means that experience is not a barrier, maybe it is the epoch and circumstances according to which the older farmers acquired their trade and which might have stressed upon the chemical solutions. The reason behind this complexity is the reason why the regression analysis, which has the overlap of these variables identified that age and experience were not unique significant predictors.

Table 6: Predictors of Integrated Pest Management Practices: Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Predictor Variable	B	SE B	β	t	p-value	VIF
(Constant)	12.45	3.21		3.88	<.001	
Knowledge Score	0.38	0.11	.32	3.45	.001	1.28
Attitude Score	0.45	0.09	.44	5.00	<.001	1.19
Age	-0.08	0.07	-.12	-1.14	.259	2.45
Farming Experience	0.05	0.06	.09	0.83	.409	2.10
Education Level	0.61	0.28	.20	2.18	.034	1.52
Farm Size	0.72	0.35	.19	2.06	.044	1.31

Model Summary: $R = .68$, $R^2 = .46$, Adjusted $R^2 = .41$, $F(6, 53) = 9.87$, $p < .001$

The multiple linear regression analysis offers effective, quantitative data on the most important factors contributing towards the adoption of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) practices among farmers. The model is both statistically significant ($F(6, 53) = 9.87$, $p < .001$) and sufficient to explain a significant 46 percent of the adoption of IPM ($R^2 = .46$). It means that knowledge, attitudes, and socioeconomic factors taken into consideration in the analysis are powerful predictors of the adoption of IPM strategies by a farmer. The Attitude Score of the farmers ($b = .44$, $p < .001$) and Knowledge Score ($b = .32$, $p = .001$) have the most significant predictors. The positive beta-weights indicate that more attitude towards sustainable practices (e.g., believing in biological control and preventive measures) and more knowledgeable farmers (e.g., knowledge about the pest life cycles and the concept of IPM) have a much higher probability of adopting IPM practices. This discovery is a vital connection between the earlier descriptive information. It establishes that the knowledge gaps and dominant attitudes (as mentioned earlier) are not mere observations but directly and significantly related to the practical inadequacies which are identified in Table 4. It can be implied that intervention programs should be two-fold, as they should both enhance ecological knowledge and change attitudes towards the idea of IPM as a complex one and remind that it is a valuable and needed system. Education Level ($b = .20$, $p = .034$) and Farm Size ($b = .19$, $p = .044$) among the socioeconomic variables came out as significant positive predictors. This suggests that those farmers who have a higher education level could be better placed to handle and process the complex

information that is needed in IPM. Likewise, the operations of bigger farms might possess more resources, both financial and in other areas, to invest in learning and adoption of new practices that might be more management intensive. This also points out a possible danger of failing to include less-educated or small-scale farmers in sustainable agriculture program unless the assistance is properly customized. Conversely, there was no significant predictors of Age and Farming Experience ($p > .05$). It is a valuable finding, given that it implies that the age and years of experience of a farmer do not necessarily deter the adoption of IPM. These factors are found not to be significant, and this in combination with the significance of knowledge and attitude implies that the mindset and knowledge of a farmer is more important to adoption than the demographic profile of a farmer. The small value of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of all predictors (all less than 2.5) implies that the issue of multicollinearity is not a problem, which makes the estimates of individual coefficients more reliable.

Conclusion

The research gives a thorough evaluation of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of farmers in South Punjab with respect to the management of the insect pest, where the system is highly reliant on the use of chemical pesticides, limited ecological knowledge, restricted economic constraints, and insufficient institutional support. Even though farmers have a high practical capacity to tell the pests, their knowledge on Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and their poor level of understanding of pest ecology practices inhibits their capacity to embrace sustainable practices. Attitudes also indicate a tendency to seek the use of chemicals, which are supported by the beliefs that IPM is complicated and time-consuming. Real operations such as poor scouting, absence of action thresholds, insufficient use of PPE and poor disposal of pesticide containers are hazards to the environment and human well being. As the analysis reveals, the factors that impact the adoption of IPM greatly are knowledge, attitudes, the level of education, and the size of the farm, but not age and experience. These observations highlight the fact that farmers access to information, their perceptions, and the availability of resources is more important in influencing behavior change in managing pests than demographic traits. The research enters into a conclusion that the enhancement of the IPM adoption should be undertaken through the well-organized interventions that develop technical knowledge of farmers, transform the attitudes to sustainable solutions, and decrease the economic and logistical obstacles. Devoid of specific support, the farmers will maintain the use of chemical based strategies that undermine the long-term productivity, environmental health and safety.

Recommendations

With the results of this research, some important recommendations will be suggested to enhance the ability of the farmers to manage pests in a more sustainable manner. To start with, there is urgent requirement to strengthen the technical knowledge of farmers on Integrated Pest Management (IPM) by organizing regular and practical training sessions, field demonstrations, and farmer field schools so that the ideas relating to pest life cycles, beneficial insects, biological control, and action thresholds are well learned and easily implemented. It is necessary to strengthen the role of the agricultural extension services, since the farmers nowadays have to use informal sources of information, which is rather biased, such as pesticide sellers. Timely and impartial advisory services and easy to understand education materials such as mobile based advisories based on various literacy levels should be offered in extension departments. Non-chemical-based control methods like biopesticides, pheromone

traps, and other environmentally friendly products should be made cheaper and more accessible through subsidies, better supply chains, and government and development partners funding. Furthermore, safety measures should be highlighted through the encouragement of regular wearing of the personal protective equipment (PPE), the ability to read the labels correctly, and the disposal of the pesticide containers in a safe and environmental way. Meanwhile, policy intervention is required to enable sustainable management of pests through encouraging the use of IPM and controlling advisory services of the pesticide retailers. There should also be special concern towards smallholders and less-educated farmers whereby they receive specific training and financial support in order to be included in sustainable agriculture programs. Lastly, participatory methods that include the involvement of progressive farmers as local trainers and encouraging peer learning can be used to improve the community level acceptance and practical adoption of IPM. All these combined can help close the knowledge gaps, attitudes gaps, and practice gaps, in order to have safer, more sustainable, and more effective pest management systems in South Punjab.

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